

Adequate Nutrition in the Italian regions

Grows in all macro-regions except in southern Italy

Istat-Bes calculates the value of adequate nutrition. The adequate nutrition is defined as "standardized proportion of 3 -year -old people and more than they consume at least 4 portions of fruit and/or vegetables daily on the total of 3 -year and more people". The data are available in the period 2005-2020.

Ranking of the Italian regions for the value of adequate nutrition in 2020. Piedmont is in the first place in the ranking of adequate nutrition in 2020 with a value of 26.7, followed by Emilia Romagna with an equal value 23.2 and the Tuscany with an amount equal to 22.8 units. In the middle of the standings there are the Aosta Valley with a value of 21, Liguria with an amount of 20.6 and Veneto with an amount of 20.4 units. Basilicata and Calabria close the ranking with an amount of 12.6 and Campania with an amount of 10.7.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage variation of adequate nutrition in the period 2005-2020. Sardinia is in the first place due to percentage variation of adequate nutrition between 2005 and 2020 with a value of 21.20% equal to an amount of 3.90 units, followed by Calabria with a value of 21.15% equal to an amount of 2.20 units and from Basilicata with a value of 17.76% equal to an amount of 1.90 units. In the middle of the standings there are Tuscany with an amount equal to 5.56% equal to an amount of 1.20 units, followed by Molise with a percentage variation equal to an amount of 5.00% equal to 0.80 units and the Liguria with an amount equal to 4.04% equal to an amount of 0.80 units. The ranking closes the Veneto with Nu value equal to -7.27% equal to an amount of -1.60 units, followed by Friuli -Venezia Giulia with a value of 14.17% equal to an amount of -3.60 Unit and Campania with a value of 26.21% equal to an amount of -3.80 units.

Italian macro-regions. Between 2005 and 2020 the value of adequate nutrition has grown in all Italian macro-regions except for the South. In Northern Italy, the value of adequate nutrition has grown from an amount of 21.00 units up to a value of 21.70 units or an amount of 0.70 units equal to a variation of 3.33%. Between 2005 and 2020 the value of adequate nutrition in central Italy grew from an amount of 21.00 units up to a value of 21.10 units or equal to an amount of 0.10 units equal to an amount of 0.48%. Between 2005 and 2020 the value of adequate nutrition decreased in southern Italy from an amount of 13.6 units up to a value of 13.4 units or equal to a variation of -0.20 units equal to an amount of -1.47%. Overall, in Italy the value of adequate nutrition has grown from an amount of 18.4 up to a value of 18.8 units or a variation of 0.40 units equal to an amount of 2.17%.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm. Below is a clusterization using the K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Two Clusters were detected or:

- *Cluster 1:* Calabria, Puglia, Molise, Basilicata, Sicily, Campania, Abruzzo;
- *Cluster 2:* Emilia-Romagna, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Tuscany, Marche, Lombardy, Umbria, Piedmont, Lazio, Trentino-Alto Adige, Liguria, Sardinia, Veneto, Valle d'Aosta.

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Calculating the median of the two Clusters is evident the dominance of Cluster 2 compared to that of Cluster 1 or: $C2 = 21.8 > C1 = 12.9$. It follows that the value of the median of adequate nutrition of the center north is equal to about 168% of the value of the southern regions. It therefore derives that the difference between central-north and south does not only operate on an income level as it also retroacts at the level of adequate nutrition. And obviously lacking adequate nutrition, it is likely that there is a greater load of southern health systems than the value of northern health systems. It follows that the health policies that act in the change in eating habits also become policies capable of prospectively reduce the health expenditure per capita at regional level.

- **Network Analysis with the use of Manhattan's distance.** Below is a network analysis network using Manhattan's distance. The data show the presence of two network structures of which one is complex and the other has a simplified structure. The complex structure consists of the following regions namely: Veneto, Lazio, Lombardy, Liguria, Trentino-Alto Adige. Relations between the Regions are indicated below:
- Veneto has a connection with Lazio with links with a value of 1.1 and with Lombardy with a value of 1.2 units;
- Lazio has a connection with Veneto with a link having a value of 1.1, and with Lombardy with a value of 1.2;
- Lombardy has a connection with Veneto with a link with a value of 1.2, a link with Lazio with an amount equal to 1.2, with Liguria with a value of 1.1, with Trentino -Toto Adige with a value of 0.87;
- Trentino-Alto Adige has a connection with Lombardy with a value of 0.87 units, and with Liguria with a link equal to 0.85 units.
- Liguria has a connection with Lombardy equal to an amount of 1.1 units and with Trentino-Alto Adige with a value of 0.85 units.

There is also a simplified link between Campania and Sicily having a value of 1.1 units.

The network structure confirms the idea of the contrast between Central-North and South and highlights on the one hand the centrality of the numerical dynamics of Lombardy in the center-north and on the other side the connection between Campania and Sicily in terms of adequate nutrition.

Machine Learning and Predictions. Below are nine Machine Learning algorithms for the prediction of the future value of adequate nutrition in the Italian regions. The algorithms were trained with 80% of the available data. In addition, a cross validation was made with 20 folds. The algorithms were compared in terms of predictive efficiency based on their ability to maximize the R-Squared and minimize the statistical errors MSE, RMSE and Mae. The data show the following system of algorithms:

1. Random Forest with a payoff value of 5;
2. ADABOOST with a payoff value of 7;
3. KNN with a payoff value of 12;
4. Gradient Boosting with a payoff value of 16;
5. SGD with a payoff value of 16;
6. Tree with a payoff value of 24;
7. SVM with a payoff value of 28;
8. Linear Regression with a payoff value of 28.

Therefore, using the Random Forest algorithm it was possible to predict the following results or:

- Piedmont with a diminutive variation from an amount of 26.70 up to a value of 22.4 or a variation of -4.26 units equal to an amount of -15.96%;
- Valle d'Aosta with an increased variation from an amount of 21.00 to a value of 21.46 or equal to a variation of 0.46 units equal to an amount of 2.19%;
- Liguria with an increased variation from an amount of 20.60 units up to a value of 21.46 units or equal to a variation of 0.34 equal to an amount of 1.65%;
- Lombardy with an increased variation from an amount of 19.70 units up to a value of 20.88 units equal to a variation of 1.18 units equal to an amount of 5.99%;
- Trentino -Alto Adige with a diminutive variation from an amount of 21.10 units up to a value of 20.73 units or equal to a variation of -0.37 units equal to an amount of -1.75%;
- Veneto with an increased variation from an amount of 20.40 units up to a value of 20.48 or equal to a value of 0.08 units equal to an amount of 0.42%;
- Friuli-Venezia Giulia with an increased variation from an amount of 21.80 units up to a value of 22.31 units or equal to a variation of 0.51 units equal to an amount of 2.33;
- Emilia -Romagna with a diminutive variation from an amount of 23.20 units up to a value of 22.65 units or equal to an amount of -0.55 units equal to -2.39%;
- Tuscany with a diminutive variation from an amount of 22.80 units up to a value of 21.63 units or equal to a value of -1.17 units equal to a variation of -5.13%;
- Umbria with an increased variation from an amount of 22.10 units up to a value of 22.30 or equal to a value of 0.20 units equal to an amount of 0.90%;
- Marche with a variation from an amount of 21,90 units up to a value of 21.57 units or equal to a variation of -0.33 units equal to an amount of -1.51%;
- Lazio with an increased variation from an amount of 19.70 units up to a value of 20.88 units or equal to a variation of 1.18 units equal to an amount of 5.99%;
- Abruzzo with an increased variation from an amount of 14.30 units up to a value of 14.49 units or equal to a variation of 0.19 units equal to an amount of 1.33%;
- Molise with a diminutive variation from an amount of 16.80 units up to a value of 13.07 units or equal to a variation of -3.73 units equal to an amount of -22.21%;
- Campania with an increased variation from an amount of 10.70 units up to a value of 13.36 units or equal to a variation of 2.66 units equal to an amount of 24.86%;
- Puglia with an increased variation from an amount of 12,90 units up to a value of 13.54 units or equal to a variation of 0.64 units equal to a variation of 4.96%;
- Basilicata with an increased variation from an amount of 12.60 units up to a variation of 14.00 units or equal to a variation of 1.40 units equal to an amount of 11.11%;
- Sicily with an increased variation from an amount of 14.00 units up to a value of 14.16 units or equal to a variation of 0.16 units equal to an amount of 1.14%;
- Sardinia with an increased variation from a value of 22.30 units up to a value of 20.44 units or equal to a value of -1.86 units equal to -8.34%.

Overall, the average value of adequate nutrition is predicted in decrease from an amount of 18.86 units up to a value of 18.79 units or equal to a variation of -0.07 units equal to an amount of -0.37 %.

Conclusions. In summary, adequate nutrition has improved in all the macro-Italian regions between 2005 and 2020 with the exception of Southern Italy. Cluster analysis shows the presence of a clear gap between the regions of Central-North Italy which have high values in terms of adequate nutrition and the southern regions that are significantly backward. The Network Analysis confirms the presence of a complex network structure between the Northern Regions which has a central element in Lombardy while in Southern Italy the dynamics of the historical series of Sicily and Campania are

significantly related. In addition, the prediction with the machine learning manifests a marginally reductive trend of adequate nutrition in the Italian regions. It should be considered that adequate nutrition performs a preventive function with respect to the probability of using the health system and therefore regions characterized by a worst performance in terms of adequate nutrition could prospectively have a growth in public spending for the main Diseases.

Declarations

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Appendix

Data instances: 9
 Features: 4
 Meta attributes: 1

	Feature 1	MSE	RMSE	MAE	R2
1	Random Forest	0.00000	0.0000	0.0113208	1.0000
2	AdaBoost	0.0103276	0.024344	0.00000	0.989389
3	kNN	0.0126049	0.029636	0.0532495	0.987367
4	Gradient Boosting+	0.0260043	0.058637	0.0689727	0.973724
5	SGD	0.0439319	0.094623	0.0905660	0.956038
6	Tree	0.0490427	0.104149	0.1088050	0.950985
7	SVM	0.1516034	0.266088	0.2356394	0.849419
8	Liner Regression	0.8220480	0.883150	0.6341300	0.177868
9	Neural Network	1.00000	1.0000	1.00000	0.0000

Predizione con il Random Forest

Regione	2020	Prediction	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Piemonte</i>	26,70	22,44	-4,26	-15,96
<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	21,00	21,46	0,46	2,19
<i>Liguria</i>	20,60	20,94	0,34	1,65
<i>Lombardia</i>	19,70	20,88	1,18	5,99
<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	21,10	20,73	-0,37	-1,75
<i>Veneto</i>	20,40	20,48	0,08	0,42
<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	21,80	22,31	0,51	2,33
<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	23,20	22,65	-0,55	-2,39
<i>Toscana</i>	22,80	21,63	-1,17	-5,13
<i>Umbria</i>	22,10	22,30	0,20	0,90
<i>Marche</i>	21,90	21,57	-0,33	-1,51
<i>Lazio</i>	19,70	20,88	1,18	5,99
<i>Abruzzo</i>	14,30	14,49	0,19	1,33
<i>Molise</i>	16,80	13,07	-3,73	-22,21
<i>Campania</i>	10,70	13,36	2,66	24,86
<i>Puglia</i>	12,90	13,54	0,64	4,96
<i>Basilicata</i>	12,60	14,48	1,88	14,92
<i>Calabria</i>	12,60	14,00	1,40	11,11
<i>Sicilia</i>	14,00	14,16	0,16	1,14
<i>Sardegna</i>	22,30	20,44	-1,86	-8,34
<i>Media</i>	18,86	18,79	-0,07	-0,37

Predizione con Random Forest

Ranking degli Algoritmi

Algoritmo	MSE	RMSE	MAE	R2	Somma
<i>Random Forest</i>	1	1	2	1	5
<i>AdaBoost</i>	2	2	1	2	7
<i>kNN</i>	3	3	3	3	12
<i>Gradient Boosting+</i>	4	4	4	4	16
<i>SGD</i>	5	5	5	5	20
<i>Tree</i>	6	6	6	6	24
<i>SVM</i>	7	7	7	7	28
<i>Liner Regression</i>	8	8	8	8	32
<i>Neural Network</i>	9	9	9	9	36

Regione	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Piemonte	★ 23,2	★ 24,8	★ 26,7	★ 26	★ 22,9	★ 26,7	★ 25,5	★ 25,3	★ 26,2	★ 23,6	★ 25,6	★ 22,3	★ 23,7	★ 22,9	★ 23,2	★ 26,7
Valle d'Aosta	★ 21	★ 20	★ 23,5	★ 27	★ 18,4	★ 20,8	★ 22,2	★ 20	★ 17,7	★ 16,5	★ 18,2	★ 20,8	★ 18,3	★ 25,6	★ 22	★ 21
Liguria	★ 19,8	★ 22,5	★ 25,2	★ 22,5	★ 24,6	★ 22	★ 18,3	★ 18,6	★ 16,6	★ 20,2	★ 19,2	★ 19,4	★ 18,5	★ 20,8	★ 20,8	★ 20,6
Lombardia	★ 17,7	★ 21	★ 23,4	★ 20,6	★ 21,8	★ 21,1	★ 19,6	★ 20,5	★ 19,2	★ 18,1	★ 20,2	★ 21,3	★ 21,1	★ 21,8	★ 19,1	★ 19,7
Trentino-Alto Adige	★ 20,9	★ 21,7	★ 24,5	★ 21,3	★ 23,4	★ 20,6	★ 19,6	★ 19,9	★ 17,2	★ 16,8	★ 18,1	★ 20,9	★ 21,2	★ 20,6	★ 21	★ 21,1
Veneto	★ 22	★ 20,7	★ 20,9	★ 21,4	★ 18,3	★ 20,5	★ 20,2	★ 18,8	★ 19,2	★ 20,8	★ 18,6	★ 21,4	★ 19	★ 19,5	★ 19,6	★ 20,4
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	★ 25,4	★ 22,7	★ 23,5	★ 25	★ 21,8	★ 25,3	★ 25,5	★ 24,2	★ 21,9	★ 19,3	★ 21,2	★ 20,1	★ 23,6	★ 22,9	★ 20,6	★ 21,8
Emilia-Romagna	★ 24,2	★ 23	★ 20,8	★ 24,4	★ 22,6	★ 25,6	★ 21,5	★ 22,5	★ 18,9	★ 21,7	★ 24,5	★ 26,7	★ 23,9	★ 22,9	★ 19,6	★ 23,2
Toscana	★ 21,6	★ 21,5	★ 18,6	★ 20,3	★ 20,4	★ 25	★ 20,6	★ 20,4	★ 17,7	★ 20,2	★ 22,5	★ 22,6	★ 21,9	★ 24	★ 18,9	★ 22,8
Umbria	★ 20,5	★ 19,9	★ 23,5	★ 21	★ 21,8	★ 22,8	★ 23,6	★ 22,2	★ 23	★ 28,2	★ 22,3	★ 24,6	★ 25,2	★ 25,9	★ 21,8	★ 22,1
Marche	★ 21,1	★ 21	★ 24,5	★ 23,7	★ 22,3	★ 19,7	★ 23,8	★ 19,3	★ 19,2	★ 21,4	★ 25,5	★ 18,3	★ 21,6	★ 20,5	★ 20,3	★ 21,9
Lazio	★ 20,6	★ 19,6	★ 21,2	★ 23	★ 19,1	★ 20,1	★ 17,3	★ 22,1	★ 21,5	★ 20,5	★ 21,9	★ 25,1	★ 20,2	★ 21	★ 19,9	★ 19,7
Abruzzo	★ 12,7	★ 17,6	★ 15,1	★ 17,3	★ 12,9	★ 12,4	★ 19,7	★ 13,3	★ 13,4	★ 17,2	★ 12,3	★ 14,2	★ 15,7	★ 16,9	★ 15,3	★ 14,3
Molise	★ 16	★ 13,1	★ 15,1	★ 14,5	★ 13,5	★ 14,7	★ 14,7	★ 11,8	★ 11,8	★ 14,7	★ 8,3	★ 11,7	★ 14,1	★ 15	★ 13,8	★ 16,8
Campania	★ 14,5	★ 13,3	★ 15	★ 14,4	★ 15,8	★ 17	★ 12,6	★ 13,7	★ 16	★ 16,4	★ 13,5	★ 15,5	★ 13,9	★ 13,9	★ 10,9	★ 10,7
Puglia	★ 12,9	★ 14,6	★ 16,1	★ 14,3	★ 12,8	★ 14	★ 11,7	★ 10,5	★ 11,9	★ 8,5	★ 10,7	★ 10,3	★ 11,7	★ 11,3	★ 14,1	★ 12,9
Basilicata	★ 10,7	★ 12,8	★ 8,9	★ 13	★ 8,4	★ 11,3	★ 9,7	★ 8,4	★ 8,3	★ 6	★ 9,3	★ 12,8	★ 12	★ 11	★ 10	★ 12,6
Calabria	★ 10,4	★ 9,6	★ 11,4	★ 13,1	★ 11,2	★ 12	★ 11,2	★ 11,2	★ 11,4	★ 10,1	★ 11,3	★ 11,4	★ 12,3	★ 14,9	★ 11,4	★ 12,6
Sicilia	★ 13,2	★ 13,2	★ 12,2	★ 15,1	★ 12,3	★ 15,2	★ 14	★ 14,3	★ 16,2	★ 13,3	★ 14,9	★ 15,5	★ 16,1	★ 16,6	★ 13,1	★ 14
Sardegna	★ 18,4	★ 21	★ 20	★ 19,8	★ 21,5	★ 20,7	★ 25,4	★ 18	★ 15,9	★ 20,3	★ 19,9	★ 23,3	★ 26,2	★ 24,8	★ 19,5	★ 22,3

Adeguata Alimentazione 2020

Variazione Assoluta Adeguita Alimentazione 2005-2020

Variazione Percentuale Adegua Alimentazione 2005-2020

Adegua Alimentazione nelle Macro-Regioni Italiane

	2005	2020	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Nord</i>	21	21,7	0,70	3,33
<i>Centro</i>	21	21,1	0,10	0,48
<i>Mezzogiorno</i>	13,6	13,4	-0,20	-1,47
<i>Italia</i>	18,4	18,8	0,40	2,17

k-Means - Orange

Number of Clusters

Fixed:

From to

Preprocessing

Normalize columns

Initialization

Initialize with KMeans++

Re-runs:

Maximum iterations:

Apply Automatically

Silhouette Scores

2	0.632
3	0.371
4	0.271
5	0.207
6	0.202
7	0.176
8	0.145
9	0.164
10	0.150
11	0.154

? | 20 | 20 | 2

2020	kNN	Tree	Random Forest	Gradient Boosting	SVM	Neural Network	Linear Regression	AdaBoost	SGD
26.7	22.36	22.025	22.4467	22.2934	20.7231	38.8851	19.0626	21.9	22.3267
12.6	13.4	12.0667	14.0072	13.298	16.7	16.7054	10.4753	12.9	11.4805
12.9	13.34	11.9667	13.5492	13.5624	16.738	13.8009	18.2715	12.6	13.9318
21.0	20.3	20.7	21.4697	21.2909	20.5337	15.6868	25.2225	21.1	22.7841
22.8	21.06	22.025	21.6369	20.944	21.1349	16.333	21.2749	21.8	21.2668
20.4	20.78	19.7	20.4849	20.6918	20.6185	10.6741	18.882	20.6	20.1659
19.7	21.44	20.05	20.8892	21.0473	20.9811	15.3619	19.742	20.6	20.2777
19.7	20.92	20.9	20.6583	21.0622	21.0343	12.6367	17.0798	21.8	20.348
14.0	13.46	15.55	14.1638	14.8078	16.636	8.89171	13.91	14.3	14.5948
12.6	13.4	12.0667	14.4845	12.5548	17.5391	20.2242	10.3354	12.6	10.7728
16.8	12.9	14.15	13.0692	12.861	14.055	10.676	11.6314	12.9	12.5036
20.6	20.82	19.7	20.9474	20.4262	20.8453	14.1738	21.8984	20.4	20.7602
22.1	23.36	24.95	22.3045	23.8032	20.9037	28.8423	27.6041	21.9	21.7308
22.3	21.18	22.15	20.4429	21.6603	20.7971	16.0529	20.6736	21.8	21.418
21.1	20.72	21.9333	20.7306	20.5014	20.6695	13.978	20.2086	20.6	20.9701
14.3	13.4	15.4	14.4947	16.3132	17.3643	8.11327	25.5615	14	16.9241
23.2	22.62	24.4	22.6452	22.3232	21.406	27.8823	25.1595	21.9	22.8255
21.9	20.72	24.95	21.5717	22.7009	21.1438	18.4238	4.41333	22.3	21.3366
10.7	14.12	15.55	13.3671	14.7629	16.8319	9.29898	14.59	14.3	15.0838
21.8	23.12	24.95	22.3095	23.7096	21.8571	27.8636	27.6709	22.8	24.8349